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Research Article

**POLYMERIC MICROPARTICLES FORMULATION OF
INSULIN FOR ORAL DRUG DELIVERY*****Chekwube A Ezegbe¹, Amarachi G Kalu², Ozioma F Orazulike³,
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Article Received: January 2022**Accepted:** February 2022**Published:** March 2022**Abstract:**

Aim: To investigate the use of polymers with mucoadhesive properties. **Method:** Microparticles were formed using double emulsion technique (w/o/w) with the insulin loaded at the core of the particles. Gelatin, Polyethylene glycol 4000 (PEG-4000), Eudragit® S 100, snail mucin and sodium alginate polymers were combined at different ratios and investigated. The subsequent batches, W (Gelatin-PEG 4000), were characterized for particle size, morphology and polydispersity index (PDI). The stability of the formulations were evaluated using pH and Differential Scanning Calorimeter (DSC). In vitro drug release profile and in vivo study using diabetic rat model were carried out on the formulations. **Results:** The batches in W, had rough spherical shapes except for batch Z3 which was rod-like and smooth. Particle size ranged from $12.24 \mu\text{m} \pm 0.1$ to $23.57 \mu\text{m} \pm 2.3$ (batch W). PDI of the optimized batches were W2 (0.884 ± 0.11), W3 (0.431 ± 0.30), W5 (0.407 ± 0.64). The pH of the formulations showed an increase from 6.4 to 6.6 (at 24 h) to 7.4 – 7.8 (after one month) on storage for batches W, indicating a secondary microbial degradation. The encapsulation efficiency across all batches were greater than 76.4 %, and the loading capacities were between 2.48 to 5.24 %. The DSC thermogram showed that when compared with a commercial sample of insulin, that the sub-batches of batch W showed greater stability than the reference sample. **Conclusion:** Polymers of mucoadhesive properties can be used to formulate insulin for oral drug delivery, and they also have potential control release ability.

Keywords: Diabetes mellitus, Insulin, Microparticles, Polymers.**Corresponding author:****Chekwube A Ezegbe,**Department of Pharmaceutical Technology and Industrial Pharmacy,
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INTRODUCTION

Diabetes mellitus is a disease condition of uttermost importance in today's society because of its high prevalence. The international diabetic Federation (IDF) reported that 366 million people were affected by diabetes in 2011 and estimated that by 2030, this number would rise to 552 million [1]. Due to its high prevalence and secondary effects, diabetes is one of the most lethal disease and responsible for almost three million deaths per year worldwide, as reported by the World Health Organization [1]. On average, life expectancy is reduced by more than 20 years in people with type 1 diabetes, and by up to 10 years in people with type 2 diabetes [2]. Prediabetes is a condition in which blood glucose levels are too high to be considered normal, but not high enough to be labeled diabetes. People have prediabetes if their fasting blood glucose level is between 100 mg/dL (5.6 mmol/L) and 125 mg/dL (6.9 mmol/L) or if their blood glucose level 2 h after a glucose tolerance test is between 140 mg/dL (7.8 mmol/L) and 199 mg/dL (11.0 mmol/L). Prediabetes carries a higher risk of future diabetes as well as heart disease. Decreasing body weight by 5 to 10 % through diet and exercise can significantly reduce the risk of developing future diabetes. [2]. In type 1 diabetes (formerly called insulin-dependent diabetes or juvenile-onset diabetes), the body's immune system attacks the insulin-producing cells of the pancreas, and more than 90 % of them are permanently destroyed. The pancreas, therefore, produces little or no insulin. Only about 5 to 10 % of all people with diabetes have type 1 disease. Most people who have type 1 diabetes develop the disease before age 30, although it can develop later in life. [3]. Scientists believe that an environmental factor—possibly a viral infection or a nutritional factor during childhood or early adulthood—causes the immune system to destroy the insulin-producing cells of the pancreas. A genetic predisposition makes some people more susceptible to an environmental factor. [4]. In type 2 diabetes (formerly called non-insulin-dependent diabetes or adult-onset diabetes), the pancreas often continues to produce insulin, sometimes even at higher-than-normal levels, especially early in the disease. However, the body develops resistance to the effects of insulin, so there is not enough insulin to meet the body's needs. As type 2 diabetes progresses, the insulin-producing ability of the pancreas decreases [5].

Type 2 diabetes was once rare in children and adolescents but has recently become more common. However, it usually begins in people older than 30 and becomes progressively more common with age.

About 26 % of people older than 65 have type 2 diabetes. People of certain racial and ethnic backgrounds are at increased risk of developing type 2 diabetes: blacks, Asian Americans, American Indians, and people of Spanish or Latin American ancestry who live in the United States have a twofold to threefold increased risk as compared with whites. Type 2 diabetes also tends to run in families [5]. Obesity is the chief risk factor for developing type 2 diabetes, and 80 to 90 % of people with this disorder are overweight or obese. Because obesity causes insulin resistance, obese people need very large amounts of insulin to maintain normal blood glucose levels [6]. Certain disorders and drugs can affect the way the body uses insulin and can lead to type 2 diabetes. Examples of common states (conditions) that result in impaired insulin use are:

- High levels of corticosteroids (most commonly due to use of corticosteroid drugs or Cushing syndrome)
- Pregnancy (gestational diabetes)

Diabetes also may occur in people with excess production of growth hormone (acromegaly) and people with certain hormone-secreting tumors. Severe or recurring pancreatitis and other disorders that directly damage the pancreas can lead to diabetes [7].

The overall goal of this project was to develop microparticles with high insulin loading, capable of delivering bioactive insulin before the microparticles get cleared. Five mucoadhesive polymers were used to formulate water-in-oil-in-water emulsion for the microparticles which have been proven to have high loading efficiency.

MATERIALS AND METHOD:

The following materials were bought from suppliers. Human recombinant insulin (Eli Lilly, USA), Eudragit® S-100 (Sigma, USA), PEG 4000 (Sigma, USA), paraffin oil (Moko pharm ltd, Lagos, Nigeria), sodium alginate (Merck, Germany), gelatin, mucin (snail), de-ionized water, Span 60, Acetone (Merck, Germany). All other chemicals used were reagent grade.

Extraction of mucin

Snail mucin powder was extracted from the African giant snail *Arachatina marginata* following the method of Adikwu [8]. The snail shells were cracked and their fleshy bodies removed from the shells with the aid of a metal rod. Excretory material accompanying the bodies were removed. The snail's bodies were subjected to washing by gently squeezing off the slime from the bodies repeatedly into a pool of

250 ml of water and decanted. This procedure was repeated several times to obtain a pool of mucus from the snail. The mucin polymer was precipitated using several liters of acetone. The precipitate was filtered and lyophilized to give brownish flakes. The dried flakes were blended in an electric blender to give mucin powders.

Preparation of the micro-particle

The ratio of gelatin and PEG 4000 used for preparing the empty microparticles are shown in Table 1 Using w/o/w double emulsion technique, one (1) gram quantity each of Gelatin and PEG 4000 ratio mixtures were dispersed in 20 ml distilled water to produce 10 % w/v homogenous dispersion. This was sonicated at an amplitude of 100 rps for 60 sec. using an ultrasonic probe (Athena technology, Virginia, USA). A 10 ml volume of insulin was added to this dispersion and sonicated using an ultrasonic probe (Athena technology, Virginia, USA). Each dispersion was transferred into a 100 ml beaker containing 10 ml of liquid paraffin using a magnetic stirrer set at a stirring speed of 300 rpm. A 400 mg weight of Span 60 was dissolved in 1 ml of ethanol as added to this stage of formulation and stirred using a magnetic stirrer at 300 rpm for 60 s. The gelatin-PEG 4000 mixture in liquid

paraffin was then slowly poured into a 500 ml beaker containing 200 ml of acetone maintained at 2 °C with continued mixing at a slower speed (200 rpm), for 10 min. The beaker was immersed in an ice jar to minimize an increase in temperature. The microparticles formed were then recovered by filtration using a filter paper size 4 (Whatman, USA). The microparticles were washed five times with 50 ml quantities of acetone at 2 °C to remove any trace of the liquid paraffin. When the acetone was evaporated, the formulation was made up to 100 ml using distilled water. The prepared microparticles were divided into two portions, one portion was lyophilized, and the other part was stored at 10 °C for further study. The procedure was repeated using gelatin-PEG 4000 ratios of 0:1, 1:0, 1:1, 1:3, and 3:1. The microparticle formulations were stored in airtight plastic bottles away from light until use.

The gelatin-mucin, gelatin-Eudragit[®] S 100, and gelatin-sodium alginate polymer ratios were prepared similarly as the method stated above with the only variation being the replacement of PEG 4000 with subsequent mucin, Eudragit[®] S 100 and sodium alginate polymers [9].

Table 1: Representation of the polymer ratios used in the formulation

Batch	Gelatin (g)	PEG-4000 (g)	Mucin (g)	Insulin (ml)	Liquid Paraffin (ml)	Span 60 (g)	Water (qs) (ml)
W0	1	1	-	0	1	0.4	100
W1	0	1	-	10	1	0.4	100
W2	1	0	-	10	1	0.4	100
W3	1	1	-	10	1	0.4	100
W4	1	3	-	10	1	0.4	100
W5	3	1	-	10	1	0.4	100

Preparation of buffers

Phosphate buffer was prepared by dissolving 2.78 g of sodium dihydrogen phosphate in 100 ml of distilled water and 3 g of disodium phosphate in another 100 ml of distilled water. A 39 ml of dihydrogen sodium phosphate was collected and mixed with 61 g of disodium hydrogen phosphate, and the solution was made up to 200 ml with distilled. This gives phosphate (PO₄)²⁻ a buffer of 0.2 m with a pH of 7.4. With the aid of standardized pH meter, the pH was adjusted to 7.2 using 1N HCl [10].

Preparation of calibration curve of insulin

The calibration curve was prepared using phosphate buffer. 0.1157 mg/ml stock solution of insulin 70/30 was prepared by making up accurately measured 1 ml (100 IU) of Humulin to 30 ml using phosphate buffer solution. Different solutions of concentration 0.01157mg/ml, 0.02314 mg/ml, 0.04628 mg/ml and 0.0785 mg/ml were prepared by diluting 2, 4, 6, 8 and 10 ml of the stock using phosphate buffer (pH 7.2). The corresponding absorbance of each of the solution

was obtained with UV- visible spectrophotometer at 271 nm wavelength, and the slope was found to 10.03 ml/mg [11].

Determination of percentage recovery values.

The microparticle from each batch was weighed after lyophilization to get the microparticle values. The percentage yield was calculated using the formula [12]:

$$\text{Percentage recovery} = \frac{W_1}{W_2+W_3} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

Where W1 = weight of microparticles recovered (g)

W2 = weight of the drug

W3 = weight of polymer + other excipient

Characterization of microparticles

Particle characteristics

SEM analysis

A scanning electron microscope SEM (Hitachi Japan, Model 3400N) was used to determine the size and surface morphology of insulin-loaded microparticles. 10 µl of the microparticle suspension was placed on a glass slide and dried at room temperature (23 ± 20 °C). The samples were fixed to the stub and gold sputtered to neutralize the charging effects before scanning in SEM with an acceleration voltage of 20KV [13].

Morphology and particle size analysis

The particle size and morphology of the microparticle were determined by computerized image analysis on a polarized light microscope. Briefly, approximately one drop of the insulin-loaded MP from each batch was placed on a slide (Mansfield, Germany) using a 1 ml dropper, it was then covered with a cover slip and viewed under a polarized light microscope. With the aid of the software in the microscope, the particle morphologies were observed, and photomicrographs were taken at x1000 magnification. The sizes of the particles were measured, and the average was taken [13].

Polydispersity Index

The mean diameter and polydispersity index of both plain and drug-loaded MPs were also measured using Zetasizer Nano-ZS (Hitachi, Japan). All samples were diluted with a fixed amount of double distilled water to obtain a suitable scattering intensity, before photon correlation spectroscopic (PCS) analysis [13].

Determination of Encapsulation efficiency (EE) and drug loading content (DLC)

The entrapment efficiency (EE %) and drug loading content (LC %) of the prepared formulation was calculated as follows the colloidal suspension of

insulin- encapsulated polysomes were centrifuged at 5000 rpm for 30 min, and the supernatant was analyzed for non-encapsulated insulin content by spectrophotometer (n = 3). The encapsulation efficiencies were determined using the following equations [13]:

$$\text{EE\%} = \frac{(\text{Total amount of insulin} - \text{Free insulin in supernatant})}{\text{Total amount of insulin}} \times 100 \quad (2)$$

$$\text{DLC\%} = \frac{(\text{Total amount of insulin} - \text{Free insulin in supernatant})}{\text{Mass of nanoparticle}} \times 100 \quad (3)$$

$$\text{Percentage yield} = \frac{\text{Actual yield}}{\text{Theoretical yield}} \times 100 \quad (4)$$

pH stability studies

The pH of each formulation was measured potentiometrically. The electrode of the pH meter was inserted into the microparticle thrice, and the mean pH value recorded after calibrating with a standard buffer of pH 7.0 [14]

Re-dispersibility and Sedimentation rate

The formulations vertically oscillated, and the amount of oscillation need to re-disperse the formulation was numerically recorded. This was recorded at 24 h, one week and one month.

The formulation was left standing and undisturbed for 48 hours and calculated as thus:

$$\text{Sedimentation rate} = \frac{(\text{Total length of the formulation} - \text{length of uppermost clear zone})}{\text{Total length of the formulation}} \times 100 \quad (5)$$

Organoleptic evaluation

The colour intensity was observed with the naked eye for an interval of 24 h, one week, and one month.

The odour change was observed with the nose when the container was opened to detect any possible change in smell across the interval of 24 h, one week and three months

The color and odour change over one month was observed and recorded at 24 hours, one week, and one month.

FTIR analysis

Infrared spectra of Gelatin, PEG 4000, mucin, Eudragit S100, sodium alginate and selected formulation batches were obtained using transmittance

mode. About 2 % w/w of each sample concerning the potassium bromide (KBr) disc was mixed with dry KBr (FT-IR grade, Aldrich, Germany). The mixture was ground into a fine powder using an agate mortar for compressing into a disc. Each disc was scanned at a resolution of 4 cm⁻¹ over a wave number region of 400 – 4000 cm⁻¹ using FT-IR spectrophotometer (Model 250, Buck Scientific, USA), coupled to a computer. The characteristic peaks of infra-red transmission spectra were recorded [16].

Differential Scanning Calorimetry

Melting transition and changes in heat capacity of all the microparticles were determined using a calorimeter (Netzsch DSC 204 F1, Germany). About 5 mg of each microparticle was weighed into an aluminium pan, hermetically sealed and the thermal behaviour determined in the range of 0 -300 °C at a heating rate of 5°C/min. Baselines were determined using an empty pan, and all the thermograms were baseline corrected [17].

In vitro studies of the insulin-loaded formulation.

The *in vitro* release profiles of the insulin-loaded microparticles was determined using a dialysis membrane technique. A 1.5 ml of the formulation (containing 0.0157 mg of insulin) was added in a dialysis membrane (MWCO 8000-10000 spectrum labs, Netherland) pretreated by soaking in phosphate buffer overnight, and 1 ml of buffer dilution (pH 7.2) was added alongside it. This membrane was tied and lowered in 500 ml phosphate buffer of 7.2 and agitated using drug dissolution apparatus at 100 rpm and 37C ± 1 °C (Glass Agencies, India). At a predetermined time, 0.5 ml of the sample was taken out at intervals of 30 min, 1 h, 2 h, 4 h, and 8 h. The aliquots removed were also replaced with a fresh phosphate buffer media. The withdrawn samples were filtered through a 0.22 µm filter (Millipore®, USA). The concentration of the released insulin in the aliquot of each sample was determined by Lowry's assay using a UV spectrophotometer at 271 nm. All of the dissolution runs were performed in triplicates. The cumulative amount of insulin release at different time intervals was calculated using the following formula and plotted against time to obtain the insulin release pattern. The above procedure was repeated using the remaining batches.

$$\frac{\text{The cumulative amount released}}{\text{Total amount of insulin}} \times 100 \quad (6)$$

Where C, D refers to the concentration of insulin in the dissolution medium and volume of the dissolution medium, respectively.

Determination of the mechanism of kinetic release.

In vitro insulin release data were then fitted to zero-order, first order, Higuchi, and Korsmeyer-Peppas models to establish the insulin release mechanism of the micro-particles [16]:

$$\text{Zero-order equation: } Q_t = Q_0 + K_0t \quad (7)$$

$$\text{First order equation: } \text{Log } Q_t = \text{Log } Q_0 + Kt/2.303 \quad (8)$$

$$\text{Higuchi equation: } Q = K_H t^{1/2} \quad (9)$$

$$\text{Korsmeyer-Peppas model: } \frac{Mt}{M_\infty} = Kt^n \quad (10)$$

Where Mt/M_∞ denotes the fraction of drug released at the time (t), K is a constant showing structural and geometric characteristic of the particles, n is mentioned as the release exponent indicating the diffusion mechanism. Values of release exponent (n) = 0.45 < n < 0.89 and 0.89 indicates Fickian (case I) diffusion, non-Fickian (anomalous) diffusion and zero-order (case II) transport respectively.

In vivo studies of insulin-loaded formulations in alloxan-induced diabetic rats

All experiments were carried out by the Federation of European Laboratory Animal Science Association (FELASA) Guide for the Care and Use of Laboratory Animals and the European Union (Council Directive 86/609/EEC) and Animal Ethics Committee of the Faculty of Pharmaceutical Sciences, University of Nigeria, Nsukka [17].

Induction of diabetes

Male Wistar rats purchased from the pharmacology and Toxicology Department, University of Nigeria, Nsukka weighing 120–170 g were housed in controlled environmental conditions of temperature and relative humidity, maintained under 22 ± 2°C and 45 to 65 %, respectively. The rats were fed with standard diet feed (Feeds BC, Nsukka, Nigeria) and were provided with tap water and libitum. Lighting was on a standard 12 h on /12 h off cycle. Diabetes was induced in rats by a single intraperitoneal injection of freshly prepared alloxan (50 mg/mL in pH 4.5 citrate) at 50 mg/kg. After two weeks, rats with fasted blood glucose levels above 250 mg/dL were used for experiments. These rats were fasted for 12 h before experiments and remained fasted for 24 h

during the experiment, but had free access to water ad libitum [18].

Protocol for the administration of insulin microparticles

The 112 diabetic rats were randomly divided into 15 groups of 7 with each group in separate cages. The different formulations of the insulin-loaded microparticles were administered intragastrically by gavage needle to rats at an insulin dose of 100 IU/kg, based on the total insulin content of the microparticles for cage 1 -9. The first control group (cage 10- 13) were administered plain formulation. The next control rats were administered with equivalent volumes of oral insulin solution (cage 14). Also, control using subcutaneous insulin (2.5 IU/kg) was applied (cage 15). The final group (cage 16) received distilled water. The rats were placed into Sixteen groups as follow;

Group 1 (7 rats) received a loaded microparticle of Gelatin: PEG-4000 (1:0)

Group 2 (7 rats) received a loaded microparticle of Gelatin: PEG-4000 (1:1)

Group 3 (7 rats) received a loaded microparticle of Gelatin: PEG-4000 (3:1)

Group 4 (7 rats) received a loaded microparticle of Gelatin: Mucin (1:1)

Group 5 (7 rats) received a loaded microparticle of Gelatin: Mucin (3:1)

Group 6 (7 rats) received a loaded microparticle of Gelatin: Eudragit S100 (1:1)

Group 7 (7 rats) received a loaded microparticle of Gelatin: Eudragit S100(1:3)

Group 8 (7 rats) received a loaded microparticle of Gelatin: Sodium alginate (0:1)

Group 9 (7 rats) received a loaded microparticle of Gelatin: Sodium alginate (1:3)

Group 10 (7 rats) received a plain microparticle of Gelatin: PEG-4000 (1:1)

Group 11 (7 rats) received a plain microparticle of Gelatin: Mucin (1:1)

Group 12 (7 rats) received a plain microparticle of Gelatin: Eudragit S100 (1:1)

Group 13 (7 rats) received a plain microparticle of Gelatin: Sodium alginate (1:1)

Group 14 (7 rats) received oral insulin dispersion

Group 15 (7 rats) received subcutaneous insulin

Group 16 (7 rats) received distilled water only

Assessment of the hypoglycemic effect of oral insulin on diabetic rats

Before the commencement of the studies, the animals fasted for 16 h. The rats were then treated according to the protocol and blood glucose concentrations determined at predetermined times of 0.5, 1, 3, 6, 9, 12 and 24 h after administration from the tip of the tail vein.

Statistical and data analysis

All experiment was repeated at least thrice. The following statistical analysis was done; one-way analysis of Variance, Duncan post-ad-hoc test, and Dunnett multi-comparison test using the instant 2.00 Macintosh software (San Diego, CA). The difference was considered as significant when $p < 0.05$.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Characterization of Gelatin- PEG 4000 polymeric microparticles.

DSC analysis

The figures 1-9 shows DSC thermograms of the microparticle of drugs and drug-loaded Microparticles while figure 10 is the overlaid DSC thermogram of the optimized matrices (representative batches), while Table 3 shows the thermal properties of the formulated polymeric microparticles matrices. DSC is an essential thermometric technique that provides the necessary thermal and crystalline structure of a material. This can be quantified by the valuation of the melting temperature T_m and then glass transition temperature T_g . The result from these values when compared to other material T_g and T_m , can be used to determine the stability of drugs after undergoing conformational changes in the polymeric system. The DSC of gelatin showed a broad melting peak of 107.41 °C with an enthalpy of -2.5mW/mg, indicating the presence of existence in the amorphous state. PEG-4000 gave a sharp melting temperature of 94.76 °C and an enthalpy of -6.90 mW/mg. The admixture of Gelatin and PEG 4000 at an equal ratio (W0 1:1) led to an increase in the melting point of 148.29 °C and an increase in enthalpy to -40.62mW/mg. DSC result of insulin showed a melting peak of 139.47°C (T_m) with the corresponding enthalpy of -97.71mW/mg. There was no partial recrystallization. This revealed the crystalline nature and purity of the drug when compared with its already reported characteristics.

Fig. 1: DSC thermogram of Gelatin.

Fig. 2: DSC thermogram of PEG-4000

Fig. 3: DSC thermogram of insulin.

NLNG, ABU Zaria: METTLER

STAR® SW 13.00

W0

NLNG, ABU Zaria: METTLER

STAR® SW 13.00

W1

NLNG, ABU Zaria: METTLER

STAR® SW 13.00

W2

Key = (Figs. 4-6): W0 (1:1) is a microparticle based on ratio of 1:1 of gelatin and PEG-4000 unloaded with insulin, W1, W2 are microparticle based on ratio of 0:1 and 1: 0 respectively of gelatin and PEG-4000 loaded with insulin.

W3

W4

W5

Key= (Figs. 7-9): W3, W4 and W5 are microparticle based on ratio of 1:1 and 1:3 and 3:1 respectively of gelatin and PEG-4000 loaded with insulin.

Fig. 10: DSC thermogram of Batch W containing A1, A2, A3, A4, A5 insulin, PEG 4000 and Gelatin in superposition
 Key: A1, A2, A3, A4, A5 are gelatin-PEG 4000 polymer microparticles in the ratio of 0:1, 1:0, 1: 1, 1:3 and 3: 1 respectively

Table 2: Thermal properties of the gelatin-PEG 4000 microparticle

Sample	Melting point (°C)	Enthalpy (W/g)
Gelatin	119.92	-2.10
PEG-4000	94.76	-6.90
W0	148.29	-40.60
W1	105.32	-18.6
W2	109.84	-4.44
W3	146.97	-12.72
W4	107.15	9.53
W5	119.69	-8.10
Insulin	138.47	-97.71

Key: W0, W1, W2, W3, W4, W5 are gelatin-PEG 4000 polymer microparticles in the ratio of 1:1 (unloaded), 0:1 (loaded), 1:0 (loaded), 1: 1 (loaded), 1:3 (loaded) and 3: 1 (loaded) respectively

The DSC result of drug-loaded microparticles showed different melting and thermal properties as depicted in Fig.4-6 Formulation containing only PEG-4000 (W1 : 0:1) gave two melting peaks (105.32°C and 132.85°C) with corresponding enthalpies of -18.6 and -16.3 mW/mg, while when only gelatin was applied (W2, 1:0), the melting peak was singular at 109.84 °C at an enthalpy of -4.44 mW/mg. When either ratio of the polymer increased, there was a reduction in the melting point when compared to the drug. Thus, when PEG-4000 ratio increased, (W4, 1:3), the melting temperature peak was 107.15 °C and enthalpy, was -9.53 mW/mg, and when gelatin ratio increased (W5, 3:1), the melting peak was 119.69 °C and enthalpy -8.10 mW/mg. It follows that W1, W2, W3, and W4 are

less crystalline than insulin and equally shows that insulin existed in the amorphous form in these polymeric microparticle ratios, encapsulating it and properly solubilizing it. Also transformation of the drug into amorphous form is an indication of the ability of the microparticle to control the drug release from the system, unlike when the drug crystallizes out from the system, which reflects that it is freely available for release [19]. Therefore, insulin, as mentioned in the ratio above, is compatible with Gelatin-PEG-4000 insulin formulation.

In another light, an equal ratio of insulin-loaded gelatin-PEG-4000 microparticle (W2, 1:1) showed an elevated melting point when compared to the drug at

146.97 °C and enthalpy of -12.72 mW/mg. When compared with the same polymer ratio but unloaded with the drug, it showed a higher melting peak at 148.29 °C and enthalpy of -40.6 mW/mg. This showed a reduction in crystallinity and lattice of the formulation, but not enough to induce drug amorphous conformation change [19].

FTIR analysis

The Figures 11-18 represents the FTIR spectra of PEG 4000, Gelatin, Insulin and PEG 4000/Gelatin/Insulin MPs. In the spectrum of insulin, the characteristics peaks at 3375 cm^{-1} attributed to the stretching vibration of OH and NH bonds. Also, stretching vibrations of aliphatic OH bonds were observed in the region of 2880 – 3000 cm^{-1} . The absorption peaks at 1658 cm^{-1} , 1543 cm^{-1} are absorbed to amide I and II bands in the structure of insulin.

The FTIR spectrum of PEG 4000 showed characteristic absorption at bands 2883 cm^{-1} (C-H stretching) 1466 cm^{-1} (-C=H deformation) 1341 cm^{-1} (-C-H deformation), 1279 cm^{-1} and 1241 cm^{-1} (C-C), 1097 cm^{-1} and 1060 cm^{-1} (C-O ester), 960 cm^{-1} and 842

cm^{-1} (C-H deformation with 1 and 2 adjacent free hydrogen).

The FT-IR spectrum of gelatin showed that the band was formed by four characteristic peaks; situated at amide-A and free water (3282 cm^{-1}), amide-I (1630 cm^{-1}), amide-II (1547 cm^{-1}) and amide-III (1239 cm^{-1}). Interaction with free water, insulin, and PEG-4000. The existence of characteristics amide bands of insulin at ~1500 cm^{-1} region of PEG 4000/Gel/Ins spectra confirmed by the presence of insulin in the composite. Furthermore, in these spectra, there were no prominent shifts of the IR bands of amide I and amide II to the other frequencies that probably could state that there was no significant denaturation of the insulin after preparation of micro-composite. This is in agreement with the DSC result indicating the compatibility of insulin in the microparticles. [20]. As the amount of polymer to gelatin ratio increased, the intensity of the broad peak increased, and when gelatin increased, the intensity reduced. This was the common theme in the FTIR spectroscopy and indicated that there was no interaction between the polymers and the insulin.

Fig.11: FTIR spectrum of insulin.

Fig.12: FTIR spectrum of gelatin.

Fig. 13 : FTIR spectra of PEG-4000

Fig . 14: FT-IR of W1 batch containing 10 ml of insulin in 0: 1 ratio of gelatin and PEG 4000

Fig. 15: FT-IR of W2 batch containing 10 ml of insulin in 1:0 ratio of gelatin and PEG 4000

Fig. 16: FT-IR of W3 batch containing 10 ml of insulin in 1:1 ratio of gelatin and PEG 4000

Fig. 17: FT-IR of W4 batch containing 10 ml of insulin in 1:3 ratio of gelatin and PEG 4000

Fig. 18: FT-IR of W5 batch containing 10 ml of insulin in 3:1 ratio of gelatin and PEG 4000

SEM analysis

Scanning electron microscopy was also used to study drug microparticles compatibility (static crystallization of the insulin-loaded microparticle), and the results indicated the compatibility of the microparticle and the insulin drug. The solubility of insulin in neutral pH was determined to be 0.022 mg%, and at the quantity used, which was 10 ml (0.035 mg %) there was no observed crystallization. However during crystallization, the polymer materials used went through different stages beginning with nucleation, and followed by unhindered growth in structure formation, the initial nucleation is characterized by the appearance of nuclei far apart from each other. This non-uniform crystallization may result in a mixture of crystals which may increase drug loading capacity. This was, however, not the case as the drug loading capacity was poor. [21]

Figure 19 shows detailed morphological features of the insulin-loaded gelatin-PEG 4000 microparticle-based on optimized parameters as presented by the scanning electron micrograph. Physical stability and cellular uptake of microparticles and nanoparticles are affected by particle size. Size distribution is affected by temperature, amount of polymer ratios used, and stirring rate on the formulation. Particle size may be a function of either one or more of the following: formulation excipients, degree of homogenization, homogenization pressure, rate of particle size growth, crystal habit of the particle [21]. Particle micrograph of the microparticle showed the structured spherical and rough porous surface of the microparticles. There was also no particle aggregation indicating the physical stability of the formulation. This could be a result of the stearic hindrance resulting from the use of PEG 4000.

Fig. 19: SEM of batch W2 (insulin loaded gelatin: PEG 4000 polymer ratio of 1:0)

Particle Size

The particle sizes of orally administered insulin-loaded microparticle significantly affect their oral absorption and bio-distribution, which ultimately determine the therapeutic efficacy of their payload. It is important to mention that although this is a microemulsion, we cannot rule out the presence of nanoparticles. Overall, the insulin-loaded gelatin: PEG 4000 microparticles were spherically shaped with a rough surface. There was also a direct correlation to the quantity of polymer used and the particle size of the microparticles. Particle size may be a function of either one or more of the following: formulation excipients, degree of homogenization, homogenization pressure, rate of particle size growth, crystal habit of the particle [21]. Presence of active drug in the formulation and the need to achieve thermodynamic stability in the absence of electrostatic repulsion are usually motivating factor to particle size change. All the unloaded batches showed a smaller size when compared with their loaded counterparts. Therefore, W0 had little change in particle size

growth. PEG 4000 as used in Batch W giving its large molecular size and hence electrostatic repulsion showed the smallest particle size change. In terms of increase in particle size after 24 h in terms of decrease in particle size, for gelatin/PEG 4000 microparticles $W4 > W5 > W3 > W1 > W2 > W0$. Additionally, the polymer concentration and the amount of surfactant added to the formulation may affect the particle size distribution.

Moreover, the size of the drug carrier also may have a pronounced effect on its degradation velocity as a result of different surface erosion rate. In this study, there was no motivation to increase the particles size by the polymeric breakdown. The only motivation was increasing encapsulation efficiency and protection of active drug. Previous studies have shown that microparticles got from the double emulsion method usually have high encapsulation efficiency and reduction of the polymeric breakdown during formulation protects insulin better.

Table 3 : Particle size of gelatin-PEG 4000 microparticles

Batch	Particle size (μm) after 24 hours
W0	12.89 \pm 23.45
W1	27.91 \pm 24.81
W2	13.47 \pm 17.43
W3	23.94 \pm 15.65
W4	31.21 \pm 18.69
W5	23.94 \pm 28.07

Key: W0 is gelatin:PEG 4000 polymer microparticles at 1:1, insulin unloaded, W1 is gelatin:PEG 4000 polymer microparticles at 0:1, insulin-loaded, W2 is gelatin:PEG 4000 polymer microparticles at 1:0, insulin-loaded, W3 is gelatin: PEG 4000 polymer microparticles at 1:1, insulin-loaded, W4 is gelatin: PEG 4000 polymer microparticles at 1:3, insulin-loaded, W5 is gelatin: PEG 4000 polymer microparticles at 0:1, insulin-loaded.

Physicochemical properties of microparticles

Table 4 shows some physicochemical properties of insulin-loaded microparticles of gelatin-PEG 4000

Table 4: Encapsulation efficiency, percentage yield and loading capacity of the formulations

Batch	EE (%)	LC (%)	Yield %
W0	-	-	84.13 \pm 0.75
W1	87.33 \pm 0.13	3.45 \pm 1.13	81.23 \pm 1.25
W2	78.84 \pm 0.24	2.23 \pm 0.96	76.43 \pm 2.93
W3	82.67 \pm 0.45	3.49 \pm 1.04	88.35 \pm 2.45
W4	81.21 \pm 1.02	5.24 \pm 1.11	91.35 \pm 1.45
W5	83.94 \pm 0.95	5.73 \pm 0.86	90.24 \pm 1.29

Key: W0 is gelatin:PEG 4000 polymer microparticles at 1:1, insulin unloaded, W1 is gelatin:PEG 4000 polymer microparticles at 0:1, insulin-loaded, W2 is gelatin:PEG 4000 polymer microparticles at 1:0, insulin-loaded, W3 is gelatin: PEG 4000 polymer microparticles at 1:1, insulin-loaded, W4 is gelatin: PEG 4000 polymer microparticles at 1:3, insulin-loaded, W5 is gelatin: PEG 4000 polymer microparticles at 0:1, insulin-loaded.

Percentage Yield

The percentage yield or recovery rates of the formulation have a direct relationship to the methodology. As shown in Table 5, It was observed that maximum yield was observed in the loaded formulation. High values (> 70%) of the percentage of the microparticles recovered from the formulations are a strong indication that the formulation technique adopted was reliable. The role of any drug delivery system (DDS) is to deliver the incorporated drug to the target tissues intact with little or no toxic effect on other organ or system.

Encapsulation efficiency and Drug Loading capacity

An essential point to judge the suitability of any drug carrier is its encapsulation capacity. Although the double emulsion method is usually considered as an efficient method for preparation of peptide-loaded MP's since they can avoid high temperatures that could produce protein denaturation. The stabilizing or emulsifying agent is another important factor. It has been recognized that a stable primary w/o emulsion plays a significant role in improving the loading efficiency of MP prepared by the w/o/w double emulsion technique. That is, the more stable the primary emulsion, the high the encapsulation efficiency as drugs do not leak out of the matrix. Span

60 is known to stabilize an emulsion by reducing surface and interfacial tension. Also, due to the mucoadhesive polymers used, there was a thickening of the aqueous phase. Similar results were obtained by Battaglia *et al* [22], who found that the addition of cholesterol to microparticles determined a significant increase in insulin encapsulation efficiency. He attributed this to the surface active properties of cholesterol which could stabilize the o/w interface, thereby minimizing the amount of the peptide which might be expelled from the lipid matrix during the preparation process. The therapeutic effect further highlighted the high encapsulation efficiency during the *in-vivo* study. The overall drug loading capacity was low and showed no significant difference ($p > 0.05$) across the sub-batches. Also, there was no correlation between the nature and ratio of polymer used. This, therefore, suggests that the insulin as a hydrophilic drug and double emulsion method used in the formulation could reduce the drug loading.

The ability of microparticles to accommodate active molecules is a crucial property expressed by the EE% and LC%. While EE% defines the ratio between the weight of entrapped AI and the total weight of API added to the dispersion, LC expresses the ratio the entrapped API and the total weight of polymers. Both EE and LC are dependent on several parameters, including the hydrophilicity of the API and excipient as well as the formulation method adopted.

Polydispersity Index

Table 5: The PDI values of selected batches

Batch	PDI
W2	0.884 ± 0.01
W3	0.523 ± 0.02
W5	0.407 ± 0.21

Key: W2 is gelatin: PEG 4000 polymer microparticles at 1:0, insulin-loaded, W3 is gelatin: PEG 4000 polymer microparticles at 1:1, insulin-loaded, W5 is gelatin: PEG 4000 polymer microparticles at 0:1, insulin-loaded.

Table 5 shows the polydispersity index of representative batches. Polydispersity Index is a representation of the distribution of size population within a given sample. PDI of the selected formulation is shown in the table above. This is usually an indication of the uniformity of the particle size. There was no correlation between the number of polymers used and their polydispersity index. Generally, monodispersity was poor. The implication of this data becomes significant when we consider that larger particles will tend to increase particle aggregation in certain organs during bio-distribution this can in effect increase the drug action on that organ especially if they

have excretory or metabolic activities. W5 (containing gelatin: PEG 4000 at 3:1) showed the best monodispersity and can be expected to have the least possible toxicity during *in vivo* studies as it will not aggregate in the liver during degradation, which will reduce the first pastime and prevent the degradation of further active drug. [23]

Stability Studies

Stability studies were done in terms of pH, organoleptic evaluation, sedimentation rate

pH studies

The pH of the different batches of MPs was measured 24 h, one week, and one month after preparation to ascertain the variation of pH with time, which could be a function of degradation of the API or excipients (Figure 20). There was a slight increase in the pH formulations of batch W within the storage period. This was also applicable to unloaded formulation (drug-free) samples whose pH continued to increase throughout the observation. There was a shift of the pH toward alkalinity even in the presence of span 60 and paraffin oil degradation this can be due to the breakdown of the polymeric subunit. For batch W (gelatin: PEG 400), there was a slight reduction in the pH for W1 (gelatin: PEG polymer ratio 0:1) and W4 (gelatin: PEG 4000 polymer ratio 1:3) within one week. However, after a month, there was an increase in the pH alongside a corresponding change in color and odour indicated the presence of facultative

microorganisms which degraded the acidic polymeric subunit to alkaline metabolites.

This can be countered by lyophilization in the presence of sucrose as a cryoprotectant to avoid lysis in the microparticles on rehydration. Also, preservatives can be used to limit microbial activities. [24]

However, the decrease in the pH of the formulation loaded with the drug is significant ($p < 0.05$) as compared to the decrease observed in the unloaded (drug-free) formulation. This indicates that the decrease in the pH may cause a change in the expected activity of the formulation. [25]. It is further suggested that such change in the pH toward acidity could be overcome by the addition of stabilizing agent probably a buffer or a preservative, since the implicated instability might be of microbial origin, during the formulation.

Fig. 20: pH result of batch W containing 10 ml of insulin in gelatin and PEG 400

Key: W0 is gelatin:PEG 4000 polymer microparticles at 1:1, insulin unloaded, W1 is gelatin:PEG 4000 polymer microparticles at 0:1, insulin-loaded, W2 is gelatin:PEG 4000 polymer microparticles at 1:0, insulin-loaded, W3 is gelatin: PEG 4000 polymer microparticles at 1:1, insulin-loaded, W4 is gelatin: PEG 4000 polymer microparticles at 1:3, insulin-loaded, W5 is gelatin: PEG 4000 polymer microparticles at 0:1, insulin-loaded.

Organoleptic Evaluation

The figure 21 represents the images collected for the various microparticles formulation batches in 24 h.

Colour and odor

No preservative was used in the formulation and degradation of the formulation was observed in the form of instability through odour. Under the refrigerated condition, microbial activities are usually very low except for the psychotropic organism *Listeria monocytogenes*; *Klebsiella pneumonia* can be introduced through the non-sterile natural and synthetic polymers used in the formulation. Degradation of the polymers released the pungent

smell and was observed after one month across the formulation. However, the lyophilized sampled did not show any change in odour across the same time duration as the major factor (water activity) which is the hub of physiological activities leading to polymer degradation has been eliminated. It would be advised that in a subsequent formulation that the polymer degradation of each of the components will be done to determine the safety of the individual degraded components and also preservatives will be used to improve the shelf life of the formulation. This is because even if the products of the degradation are deemed safe, aesthetic matters to the patient as this can affect patient compliance to therapy.

Fig. 21: Image of Batch W formulation (gelatin PEG 4000) after 24 h.

Key: W0 is gelatin:PEG 4000 polymer microparticles at 1:1, insulin unloaded, W1 is gelatin:PEG 4000 polymer microparticles at 0:1, insulin-loaded, W2 is gelatin:PEG 4000 polymer microparticles at 1:0, insulin-loaded, W3 is gelatin: PEG 4000 polymer microparticles at 1:1, insulin-loaded, W4 is gelatin: PEG 4000 polymer microparticles at 1:3, insulin-loaded, W5 is gelatin: PEG 4000 polymer microparticles at 0:1, insulin-loaded.

Table 6: Representation of the change in color of formulation in 24 hours, one week and one month

Batch	24 hours	One week	One month
W0	milky white	milky white	milky white
W1	milky white	milky white	milky white
W2	milky white	milky white	milky white
W3	milky white	milky white	milky white
W4	milky white	milky white	milky white
W5	milky white	milky white	milky white

Key: W0 is gelatin:PEG 4000 polymer microparticles at 1:1, insulin unloaded, W1 is gelatin:PEG 4000 polymer microparticles at 0:1, insulin-loaded, W2 is gelatin:PEG 4000 polymer microparticles at 1:0, insulin-loaded, W3 is gelatin: PEG 4000 polymer microparticles at 1:1, insulin-loaded, W4 is gelatin: PEG 4000 polymer microparticles at 1:3, insulin-loaded, W5 is gelatin: PEG 4000 polymer microparticles at 0:1, insulin-loaded.

Table 7: Representation of the odour change of formulation in 24 hours, one week and one month

Batch	24 hours	One week	One month
W0	nil	nil	yes
W1	nil	nil	yes
W2	nil	nil	yes
W3	nil	nil	yes
W4	nil	nil	yes
W5	nil	nil	yes

Key: W0 is gelatin:PEG 4000 polymer microparticles at 1:1, insulin unloaded, W1 is gelatin:PEG 4000 polymer microparticles at 0:1, insulin-loaded, W2 is gelatin:PEG 4000 polymer microparticles at 1:0, insulin-loaded, W3 is gelatin: PEG 4000 polymer microparticles at 1:1, insulin-loaded, W4 is gelatin: PEG 4000 polymer microparticles at 1:3, insulin-loaded, W5 is gelatin: PEG 4000 polymer microparticles at 0:1, insulin-loaded.

Sedimentation rate and Re-dispersibility

The sedimentation rate is usually subject to the viscosity of the suspension formulation, existence of microparticle, wettability of the polymer. Given that the polymers used had mucoadhesive properties and thus were wettable, this was expected. Also, an

increase in the particle size on storage due to precipitation and agglomeration further increased the sedimentation rate. Batch W (PEG 4000/Gelatin/Insulin) formulation showed the least change in sedimentation rate decreasing over the observed time as the microparticles did not increase

drastically in size to warrant a gravitational effect. This is in part to the solubility of the individual components used in the medium of formulation water and also due to the stearic hindrance conferred on the formulation by the large molecular weight of PEG 4000. The increase in sedimentation rate after one

week could be due to the absorption of moisture by the microparticle complex and which increases the particle size and makes them sediment. Redispersion of the suspension was relatively easy and the polymeric ratio did not affect their property.

Fig. 22: Sedimentation rate for batch W (gelatin: PEG 4000)

Key: W0 is gelatin:PEG 4000 polymer microparticles at 1:1, insulin unloaded, W1 is gelatin:PEG 4000 polymer microparticles at 0:1, insulin-loaded, W2 is gelatin:PEG 4000 polymer microparticles at 1:0, insulin-loaded, W3 is gelatin: PEG 4000 polymer microparticles at 1:1, insulin-loaded, W4 is gelatin: PEG 4000 polymer microparticles at 1:3, insulin-loaded, W5 is gelatin: PEG 4000 polymer microparticles at 0:1, insulin-loaded.

***In vitro* drug release profile and kinetic study**

Figure 23 shows the *in vitro* drug release profile of insulin-loaded gelatin-PEG 4000 microparticles. The release of insulin from the microparticles were compared among the formulation for a period of 8 h. Insulin tends to ionize in a basic environment provided by phosphate buffer (pH 7.2). Thus, drug release testing was carried out in phosphate buffer to provide sink condition. The formulation was designed to possess sustained-release properties

The release of the entrapped protein is triggered by the degradation of the polymer by erosion, followed by the diffusion of the protein through the channels created in the process [24]. Thus, the erosion process is known to generate oligomers that can easily interact with the encapsulated protein. Leading to its denaturation [26]. Studies have shown that insulin release is optimal at pH 7.2 -7.4 and not 1.2. No burst effect was observed, indicating the drug homogeneously dispersed in the matrix gel formulation and that no significant amount of drugs were adsorbed onto the microparticle surface.

Drug release was gradual, indicating that the insulin API was entrapped in the matrix of the microparticles. The slow-release pattern of the formulation can also be attributed to the slow rate of hydration and swelling of the gel formulation in phosphate buffer. This consequently, affects the build-up of the drug in the dissolution media, which plays to our advantage. Also, because there is a plateau in the diffusion time alongside an increase in drug concentration, erosion of the microparticles alongside diffusion is implicated in the release mechanism of the drug. Gelatin and PEG 4000 both possess swelling properties. According to the obtained results, clearly, one could say the gelatin alone should not be used as a carrier for controlled release of insulin because the release time is very low. Also, to investigating the effect of the amount of polymer on the release time, different amount of polymer was prepared as stated in Table 2.

When the gelatin/PEG 4000 showed the controlled release of the insulin. The formulation showed the

incomplete release of the insulin into the 8th hour with maximum release of 63.15% for W5 at the 8th hour. There was no burst release, and when ranked in order of decreasing order, we have W5 (gelatin: PEG 4000 ratio 3:1) > W3 (gelatin: PEG 4000 ratio 1:1) > W2 (gelatin: PEG 4000 ratio 1:0) > W4 (gelatin: PEG 4000 ratio 1:3) > W1 (gelatin: PEG 4000 ratio 0:1). This is due to the mucoadhesive and wetting tendency of both gelatin and PEG 4000, which retards the release of insulin from the polymer matrix. W5 (gelatin/PEG 4000 3:1) having a higher concentration of gelatin, therefore, created more pores to allow the exit of the insulin from the medium. Summarily, an increase in

the concentration of gelatin leads to an increase in diffusion and erosion time, which increase drug release into the dissolution media.

By using the various important mathematical models like zero order, first order, Higuchi's and Korsmeyer Peppas, the *in vitro* drug release behavior of batches were investigated kinetically. According to the obtained R² values of the curves for various mathematical models, it was shown that there was a very good fitting between the experimental data and the Korsmeyer Peppas' model.

Fig. 23: *In- vitro* release of insulin comparison from microparticles formulated using different ratios of gelatin: PEG 4000. Data represented a mean SD (n = 3)

The result of the kinetic parameter (R² and n) were gotten from the different kinetic models. The results related to the *in vitro* release experiment are shown in table 8. The result indicated that the average best fit was observed for the Korsmeyer Peppas and Higuchi model. Therefore both diffusion and carrier erosion controlled the release of insulin from the microparticle

formulation. The Korsmeyer Peppas model for the insulin-loaded microparticles gave n values lower than 0.45, indicating that the release pattern was through Fickian diffusion through erosion of the surface of the microparticles. The release of insulin from the microparticles showed that it was not pH-dependent, but a factor of the erosion rate of the polymers during the diffusion of the drug.

Table 8: The first, second-order, Higuchi and Kors Meyer Peppas model of drug release determination

Batch	Zero-order	First-order	Higuchi's	Korsmeyer's Peppers	
	R ²	R ²	R ²	R ²	n
W1	0.7482	0.7482	0.86622	0.919	0.203
W2	0.9527	0.9527	0.967	0.9409	0.174
W3	0.7555	0.7555	0.8762	0.9388	0.225
W4	0.8252	0.825	0.9295	0.9759	0.280
W5	0.8768	0.8768	0.961	0.9679	0.386

Key: W1, W2, W3, W4, and W5 are insulin-loaded gelatin-PEG 4000 microparticles at a ratio of 0:1, 1:0, 1:1, 1:3 and 3: 1 respectively

***In vivo* drug study**

Figure 24 showed the hypoglycaemic effect of insulin-loaded gelatinated polymers shell microparticles on the alloxan treated diabetic mice model. The procedure previously mentioned was carried out, and the variation in the average blood glucose levels after insulin administration either by the oral route or by subcutaneous injection were plotted against time. The subcutaneous insulin administration and the plain formulation were given as control to determine the gastro-protective and drug-releasing effect of the formulation. Upon subcutaneous insulin administration, the blood glucose level began to decrease significantly within one h and reached 45 mg% at the second-hour post-injection. The blood glucose level subsequently increased with time, returning to 80 mg% after 12 h (Fig. 24). Oral insulin only was unable to produce a hypoglycemic effect in the diabetic rat. Unloaded dose-treated diabetic mice did not show any significant change in blood glucose level during the long fast time. It also eliminated the probability of the polymers having hypoglycemic activity. However, insulin-loaded gelatin/polymer MP (100I U/kg) showed hypoglycemic effect, the blood glucose level decreased to 37 mg% at the third-hour post-administration, and the effect was sustained up to 24 h.

After 24 h, the hypoglycemic effect was higher with gelatin/polymer, demonstrating the relative cumulative reduction in glucose blood level after oral administration of W2, (gelatin: PEG 4000, 1:0) W3 (gelatin: PEG 4000, 1:1), W5 (gelatin: PEG 4000, 3:1). W2 and W5 outperformed W2 ($p > 0.05$). In terms of formation of pores to necessitate the release of the active drug, the role of gelatin was observed to increase the release of insulin through diffusion as it was easier to erode and lead to channel formation for the drug. Thus as the concentration of gelatin increase, so did the rate of release.

Concerning the formulation of W2 containing insulin-loaded gelatin-PEG 4000 ratios of 1:0: previous works have shown that gelatin alone can provide gastro protection for the active drug but not sufficiently to control the release of the drug. However, the formulation showed continues to release into the 24 hours, suggesting that the release was controlled. This can be attributed to the fact that the gelatin used contained both high molecular and low molecular [27; 28].

Thus owing to the ease of drug release, the blood glucose level was down to 44 mg% at the one h mark and 23 mg% at the six h mark. This blood sugar concentration was maintained continuously for 24 h. When the concentration of gelatin was increased as seen in batch W5 (with gelatin: PEG 4000 ratio at 3:1), there was no significant change ($p < 0.05$) in the rate of hypoglycemic activity when compared to other insulin-loaded formulation. At the 1 h mark, the blood sugar concentration reduced to 47 mg% and 31 mg% at the 6 h mark. It is, however, worth noting that except for W3, the investigated insulin-loaded formulations competed favourably with the subcutaneously administered insulin reducing the blood sugar concentration to 44 mg% at 30 min. This can further suggest that the formulation can be given to patients who insist that only ora route of administration be met to improve their quality of life, without compromising pharmacological results.

Overall, the Fig. 24, demonstrates it significantly higher when the insulin (100 IU/kg) was administered orally through the microparticles delivery system compared with the control group (orally administered insulin solution, 100 IU/kg).

Fig. 24: Blood glucose level after a single oral administration of insulin solution (100IU/kg), insulin loaded microparticle (W2, W3, W5) at 100 IU/kg, unloaded microparticles and SC injection of insulin (2.5IU/kg). Data represented the mean \pm SD n = 7 per group

Key: W0, W2, W3, and W5 are plain gelatin-PEG 4000 microparticles, gelatin-PEG 4000 microparticles at 0:1 ratio, gelatin-PEG 4000 microparticles at 1:1 ratio, gelatin-PEG 4000 microparticles at 3:1 ratio respectively.

CONCLUSION:

The study shows that gelatin-Eudragit S100 containing insulin exhibited good physicochemical, property, and hypoglycemic activity. It, however, does have only the disadvantage of being slow acting as the onset of activity was observed to be 1 h from the administration.

The other selected batch formulation in W3, has also proven the hypoglycemic regulatory property and can be used as carrier for gastro-protected delivery of insulin.

Recommendation

Further work would seek to investigate the lyophilization, reconstitution of gelatin-Eudragit S100 formulation for pediatric suspension formulation. Also, long term stability test would be advocated and its hypoglycemic activity re-investigated when other polymeric components are added to make a suspension.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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